

THE MAGIC OF THE WORD IN THE PROCESS OF ARTISTIC TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will talk about the skills of artistic translation and several successful methods used in the direction of translation. Undoubtedly, the need to translate Uzbek literature, including poetry into Russian, arose for certain historical and social reasons, and Alexander Faynberg was one of the leaders in this field. The wider the range of topics studied in Uzbek literature and its translation, the wider the scope of unexplored topics. During the reading of the article, from the point of view of translation, it is possible to know that the recreation of poetic art in the artistic translation is not only one of the necessary conditions for giving the national originality reflected in the work, but also the preservation of the artistic juice of the original, the difference in terms of achieving emotional poetic translation has been analyzed and interpreted for centuries by philologists, poets, poetic scientists, specially engaged in the issues of poetic translation, and examples of the work of these poets are presented.

Artistic translation involves a complex creative process. Therefore, we rightly call the representative of this sphere a poet-translator. In a prose game, there is a plot, composition, narration and solution of events. That's why teacher poet Askad Mukhtar Talib, the translator is not a painter, he works as an artist, and through various methods of translation, including metonymic, transformational, implicit (hidden) meanings expressed (mufassal), the author seeks to convey his opinion to the reader more accurately. But the four lines translate the tone and lyrical

performance in the poem to the extent that it takes place from the reader's heart, it is necessary to have poetic inspiration and skill. The main feature of artistic translation comes from the artistic task of the language. Language becomes an aesthetic phenomenon in artistic work. The language of literary work is a separate element of "artistic reality". In translation, there is a process of transferring the artistic meaning of this figurative expressive language to the figurative expressive ground of another language, re-representing the image. Therefore, the

translator re-perceives the process of artistic reflection of events in the work. Based on the requirements of modern translation, the translator must re-create the unity of form and content as a work of art, maintain national and individual characteristics. Restoration of the national form of the work of art is one of the important problems of artistic translation. In particular, the translation of poems from Russian into Uzbek requires a strong will and perseverance from the creator. Alexander Faynberg Arkadyevich also conducted extensive research in the field of translation, and he published in Moscow the poem "Rebellion of the spirits" by Erkin Vohidov, and in Tashkent the collection "White Tower", which is considered a collection of translations from the works of Uzbek poets. [1] Every product of his creativity does not remain without the admiration of the person. The translator re-inspired the poem, which was in harmony with his soul. Information should be noted that the work and activity of Alexander Faynberg are studied by many Uzbek scientists in various spheres. I must say that although Alexander Faynberg writes in Russian, it was not so difficult for me to understand it. Because it is enough to understand the images and symbols of the poet's poems, his soul, form and content. I spoke in Uzbek only what I understood. It's like watching a unique architectural monument and describing it as if it was this kind of those who did not see it, columns, it's kind of a feat. In this regard, I will give an example of the wonders of Alexander Faynberg's poetry, his artistic works and draw your attention to its Uzbek forms. [2] The poems of Alexander Faynberg, it is drawn from simple human feelings to

universal problems in pencil. He encourages people to embrace their pure, noble feelings, save human nature and the world from crisis. The well-being of the universe, the happiness of man, knows that he is holistic with the progress of the society in which he lives. When others are happy, I can not be unhappy, when others are unhappy, he says that I can not be happy. It calls on all members of the society to be united by the development of the hometown. In particular, I tried to translate the poem "word" into English, which was turned into Uzbek by Rustam Musurman, who is interested in the work of Alexander Faynberg and is engaged in silly - creative research in this regard, and I understand that in the work of the poet there are different colourful concepts. We will focus on the following lines:

Poezd kechikishi oddiy voqea,

Samolyotni kutib ichikadi ko'z.

Haqiqiy baxtsizlik, katta fojia –

Mabodo kechiksa kutilyotgan so'z. [3, 27-page]

We will try to discuss these sentences in the case of translation into English:

Train delay is an everyday occurrence,

My eyes are yearning for waiting for the plane.

Real misfortune, a great tragedy would be-

If the expected word is too late.

The first of these lines mentioned come from vehicles like "train" and "plane" in the same place because the reader may not be able to contemplate the contents of the poem. Why are these words quoted? What

does the poet mean by this? Another feature characteristic of Faynberg's poems is a full-fledged drawing of the landscapes of the human psyche. Whatever the poet does not write on the subject, he sees the work, as proceeding from the "spirit desire", as Navoi insists. Alexander was not among the poets who were satisfied with the image of his moods. He compared these Egyptians with the events that we understandably encounter in our everyday life. Likewise, the word being said is described as being late when a person is missing something. In the following sentences, the overview is described as confused, but the meaning remained:

So'ngan gulxan uzra bo'lgandek pushmon,
Kimsasiz kulbaga boqqandek mahzun.
Kechikkan so'z g'arib, yig'laydi yomon,
Uni kecha kutgan odamlar uchun.

The art of animation is used in these lines. Words that are delayed because of how many words need to be said are left without saying, expressed in such impressive phrases as "regret", "gloomy" and "crying badly."

English translation:

Over an extinguished fire as if remorseful
To a lonely hut as if sadly look.
Delayed word is poor, crying badly,
For the people waiting for it last night.

"The nightingale's evangelical journey sounds as pleasant to everyone as the poem of the fiery poets also resonates in all corners of the world, fascinates everyone, fascinates everyone, " said one of the teachers. Therefore, although the content

of this poem sounds in different languages, its original meaning is preserved in its original form. Essence:

Kechikkan so'z bois o'rmonlar yetim,
Bepoyon yerlarning peshonasi sho'r.
Qabrlar qoshida so'z ham beso'z, jim,
Ruhlar bezovtayu qismat ko'zi ko'r.

Translation form:

Because of dallying words, forests are orphans,

Vast lands are unfortunate.

Around the graves, the word itself is speechless, silent,

Soul is concerned, the eye of fate is blind.

So the poems of Alexander Faynberg spoke Uzbek. I also looked for news from the poems of Alexander Faynberg — I translated his poems, which the poet wrote, wishing to change both himself and others. The genres of Alexander Faynberg's poetry are diverse: epic, poem, film, quartet, and sonnet. He calls his sonnets free sonnets. [4] This retains the form of a sonnet but wants to innovate in the way of expression, content and spirit of the work, and free. This means that the command to translate poetry created in the eastern language into another language is incredibly difficult and laborious. To perform such a creative task, it is not enough that you are an amateur translator, you need to live in it, you need to relate your destiny and during to oriental poetry. Only then can you understand and feel the meaning of the language, mystery of this great poem, says the poet. Alexander Faynberg also achieved a high rank in his

fate for connecting his fate with Uzbek poetry and literature and selflessly serving this land and this person during his creative and social activities.

In conclusion, it should be said that in changing the worldview of man, motivating him to understand himself, to live consciously, educating the younger generation as a perfect person, in enriching

our spirituality, the poems of the poet like Alexander Faynberg are very important. The poems of the poet Alexander Faynberg in changing the worldview of man, motivating him to understand himself, to live consciously, to educate the younger generation as a perfect person, to enrich our spirituality are important to learn and do research on them.

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